

“AN ECONOMIC ANALYSIS ON MARKETING OF POULTRY FEED OF NUTRIKRAFT IN GANJAM DISTRICT OF ODISHA”

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Abstract:

The Present study was conducted in the year 2022- 2023 with a sample of 80 Poultry Farmers in Chhatrapur Block of Ganjam district of Odisha. The Poultry Respondents were divided into three size groups on the basis of the number of birds raised viz. below 50, 51-100 and above 100. A total of 80 respondents were selected and the data was collected with the help of schedule. The study reveals that the farmers were having small farms (45%) followed by (35%) medium and (20%) large farms. It has been seen that most respondents live in nuclear families (75%) and (25%) in joint families. The study also revealed that the small farmer has an annual income up to 20,000 followed by medium farmer has the annual income between 20,000 to 50,000 and the large farmer is having annual income above 50,000 per year. The two marketing channels prevalent in the marketing of poultry feed. The price spread in the first and second channel was Rs.194, Rs.224 percent respectively. The total marketing costs in the first and second channel was Rs. 74, and Rs. 114 respectively. The marketing efficiency in first and second channel was 6.33% and 6.47% respectively and producer's Share in consumer rupees of first and second channel was 79.29% and 76.65% respectively. The major constraints of poultry feed marketing are presented by ranking in the present study were High cost of transportation (1st), Price fluctuation (2nd), Delayed sales (3rd), Shortage of trading (4th), High prices (5th), Storage problems (6th), High-cost storage (7th).

Keywords: Marketing channel, price spread, marketing cost, marketing efficiency, Producers share in consumer rupees.

Introduction:

Poultry feed is food for farm poultry, including chickens, ducks, geese, and other domestic birds. Before the twentieth century, poultry was mostly kept on general farms, and foraged for much of their feed, eating insects, grain spilled by cattle and horses, and plants around the farm. This was often supplemented by grain, household scraps, calcium supplements such as oyster shells, and garden waste. As farming became more specialized, many farms kept flocks too large to be fed in this way, and nutritionally complete poultry feed were developed. Modern feeds for poultry consist largely of grain, protein supplements such as soybean oil meal, mineral supplements, and vitamin supplements. The quantity of feed, and the nutritional requirements of the feed, depending on the weight and age of the poultry, their rate of growth, their rate of egg production, the weather (cold or wet weather causes higher energy expenditure), and the amount of nutrition the poultry obtain from foraging. This results in a wide variety of feed formulations. The substitution of less expensive local ingredients introduces additional variations. Healthy poultry require enough protein and carbohydrates, along with the necessary vitamins, dietary minerals, and an adequate supply of water. Lactose-fermentation of feed can aid in supplying vitamins and minerals to poultry. Egg laying hens require 4 grams per day of calcium of which 2 grams are used in the egg. Oyster shells are often used as a source of dietary calcium. Certain diets also require the use of grit, tiny rocks such as pieces of granite, in the feed. Grit aids in digestion by grinding

food as it passes through the gizzard. Grit is not needed if commercial feed is used. Calcium iodate is used as supplement of iodine.

Material and Method:**Selection of the District:**

There are 30 District and 3 division in Odisha state. Out of this Ganjam district of Odisha was selected for the present study based on maximum area under vegetable, Paddy, Wheat Cultivation and poultry farm owner.

Selection of Block:

There are 22 blocks in the district. Out of these Chhatrapur was selected purposively for the study.

Selection of Village:

A complete list of all villages of Chhatrapur block was obtained from the block development office. Thereafter these villages were arranged in ascending order based on the area of Poultry farming. Thus, out of total villages 5% of villages were selected randomly for the present study.

Selection of Farmers:

From the selected village list of all the poultry farmers obtained from the village development office in each selected village. For the selection of cultivators from families was listed and 10% farmers was randomly selected from each village and then farmers were classified in to three group based on rearing ability.

Table 1: Selection of Respondents:

District	Block	Village	Sample	Respondents			Total
				Small	Medium	Large	
Ganjam	Chhatrapur	Bipulingi	35	18	11	6	35
		Sundarpur	23	9	9	5	23
		Padmavati	22	9	8	5	22
			80	36	28	16	80

Analytical Tools**Standard Deviation:**

Mean

$$\sigma = \sqrt{\frac{\sum(x_i - \mu)^2}{N}}$$

$$m = \frac{\text{sum of the terms}}{\text{number of terms}}$$

Marketing EfficiencyConsumer paid price

Total marketing cost + Total marketing margin

Marketing Margin:

Marketing Margin = Product price - raw material

Price Spread

Consumer paid price – Net price received by producer

Table 2: Category of the Farmer

Sr. No.	Category	Value	Percentage
1.	Small	36	45%
2.	Medium	28	35%
3.	Large	16	20%

Table 2 reveals Farm size is one of the prime socio-demographic variables in this study. As farm size affects the buying decision, it has an essential association in market-related research. Due to the distinction in their perception and socialization, farm size tends to

Table 3: Age of Respondents

Sr. No.	Particulars	Small	Medium	Large	Total
1.	Young (20-35 years)	11 (13.75%)	10 (12.25%)	5 (6.25%)	26 (32.25%)
2.	Middle (36-50 years)	16 (20%)	12 (15%)	9 (11.25%)	37 (46.25%)
3.	Old (above 50 years)	9 (11.25%)	6 (7.5%)	2 (2.5%)	17 (21.50%)

Table 3 reveals that One of the critical socio-demographic factors in this study is Age. Age is given such importance in market-related research because it affects the physical and psychological aspect of the consumer, which, in turn, affects his/her buying behaviour. From

Table 4 : Education

Sr. No.	Particulars	Small	Medium	Large
1.	Primary	7 (8.75%)	1 (1.25%)	0 (0%)
2.	High School	10 (12.5%)	7 (8.75%)	4 (5%)
3.	Intermediate	8 (10%)	9 (11.25%)	5 (6.25%)
4.	Graduation & above	6 (7.5%)	7 (8.57%)	7 (8.57%)
5.	Illiterate	5 (6.25%)	4 (5%)	0 (0%)

Table 4 Another socio-demographic factor considered in this consumer behaviour study is education. From the table below among 80 respondents, 9 respondents found to be illiterate. The highest number of respondents were found to have intermediate degree qualification. They constitute 22(27.05%) 21(26.25%) were found

Table 5: Family Size

Sr. No	Particulars	Family type	Percentage (%)
1.	Up to 5 members	Nuclear	75%
2.	More than 5 members	Joint	25%

Table 5 reveals that is one of the Family type socio-demographic variables in this study. As family affects the buying decision, it has an essential association in market-related research. Due to the distinction

Producers Share in Consumer's Rupees:

$$\frac{\text{Net price received by producer}}{\text{Consumer Price}} \times 100$$
Garrett Ranking

$$100 (R_{ij} - 0.5) / N_j$$
Result And Discussion

The result is a presentation of the findings of the given study, purely based on the objectives:

- To study socio economic status of respondent in the study area.
- To identify the marketing channel involved in the study area.
- To find out the price spread, marketing efficiency, marketing margin and producer's share in consumer rupees of Nutria kraft poultry feed marketing in study area.
- To assess the problems in the marketing of Nutrikraft poultry feed.

have distinct conclusions while buying. Out of the total, 80 respondents 36 respondents were having small size farm, 28 were having medium size farm and remaining 16 were having large size farm.

this Table it can be concluded that 26(32.05 %) respondents are at the young age group of 20-35, 37(45.67%) respondents are in the middle age group of 36-50, 17(21.25%) respondents are in old age of above 50. Therefore, most respondents are in the middle age group of 36-50.

that they are qualified till high school, 20(25%) were found that they are qualified till Graduation and above and 8(10%) were qualified till primary school. Thus, it can be seen majority among all is intermediate category which is 22(27.05%)

in their perception and socialization, joint family and nuclear family tend to have distinct conclusions while buying. Out of the total, 8-respondents 60 respondents were male, that is 75% while the Remaining 20 were nuclear family that is 25% of total sample.

Table 6: Annual Income

Sr. No	Category	Annual Income
1.	Small	Up to 20,000
2.	Medium	20,000 – 50,000

3.	Large	Above 50.0000
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Table 6 Annual Income Another very crucial socio-economic variable is monthly income that directly impacts the consumer buying behavior as it is closely associated with the economic aspect. Information about income was collected on an annual basis. From the Table 6, small category respondents earn up to 20,000 per year followed by medium category farmer 20,000-50,000 yearly and large category farmer earn above 50,0000 yearly.

Table 7: Preference of marketing Channels in marketing of Nutrikraft poultry feed in the study area.

Table 8: Price Spread, Marketing Efficiency, Marketing Margin and Producer Share in Consumer Rupees Of Nutri Kraft Poultry Feed Marketing Through Channel 1.

Channel – I - Producer – Wholesaler - Consumer
Channel – II- Producer- Wholesaler – Retailer- Consumer

Sr. No.	Channel Type	No of Respondents	Percentage
1.	Channel – I	30	37.5%
2.	Channel - II	50	62.5%

Table 7 Reveals the preferred marketing channel by the respondent farmers for purchasing poultry feed is 30 (37.50%) for channel 1 and 50(62.50%) for purchasing poultry feed.

S. No	Particulars	Value in Rupees/50kg bag
1.	Producer sale price to wholesaler	1300
2.	Cost incurred by the producer	
I	Packing cost	10.00
ii	Packing material cost	10.00
iii	Transportation cost	12.00
iv	Market cost	10.00
v	Labour cost	07.00
vi	Loading and Unloading cost	05.00
vii	Miscellaneous charges	18.00
viii.	Weighing charges	2.00
	Total cost (i-vii)	74.00
3.	Margin of Producer	150.00
4.	Net price received by producer	1,226
5.	Wholesaler sale price to Consumer	1420
	Marketing cost	74
6.	Marketing Efficiency	6.33%
7.	Price Spread	194
8.	Producer's Share in Consumer Rupees	79.29%

Table 8 Above table reveals the marketing cost, marketing margin and marketing efficiency of the product in channel-I, Producer sale price to Wholesaler was 1300 rupees while consumer paid price was 1420 rupees.

Table 9: Price Spread, Marketing Efficiency, Marketing Margin and Producer Share in Consumer Rupees Of Nutri Kraft Poultry Feed Marketing Through Channel 2.

Channel II

Producer –Wholesaler – Retailer – Consumer

Sr.	Particulars	Value in Rs. /50kg bag
1.	Sales price of Wholesaler to Retailer	1400
2.	Cost incurred by the Wholesaler	
I	Loading & Unloading charges	5
Ii	Carriage up to shop	5
Iii	Weighting charges	5
Iv	Town charges	10
V	Transportation	10
Vi	Losses & Miscellaneous charges	5
	Total Cost (i-vi)	40.00
3	Margin of Village Merchant/Retailer	50.00
5.	Consumers paid price	1450
6.	Total marketing cost	114
7.	Total marketing margins	110
6.	Marketing Efficiency	6.47%
7.	Price Spread	224
8.	Producer's Share in Consumer Rupee	77.65%

Table 9 In the above table we can see the marketing cost, marketing margin, price Spread and Producer's Share in Consumer Rupees and the marketing efficiency of Channel- II, Wholesaler sales price to retailer is 1400 and consumers paid price is 1450 in this Channel.

Table 10: Constraint in marketing of Nutrikraft poultry feed in the study area.

Sr. No.	Constraints	Frequency	Ranking
1.	High cost of transportation	20	I
2.	Price fluctuation	12	III
3.	Delayed sales	4	VII
4.	Shortage of trading	14	II
5.	High prices	10	V
6.	Storage problems	9	VI
7.	High-cost storage	11	IV

Table 10 The major marketing constraints were High cost of transportation with 20 respondents' response out of total sample ranked I. Shortage of trading with 14 respondents' response out of total sample ranked II. Price fluctuation with 12 respondents' response out of total sample ranked III. High-cost storage with 11 respondents' response out of total sample ranked IV, High prices with 10 respondents' response out of total sample ranked V, Storage problems with 9 respondents' response out of total sample ranked VI and Delayed sales with 4 respondents' response out of total sample ranked VII.

Conclusion:

Majority of the poultry farm owner have small farm as compared to large farm. In the survey it was seen that 45% of small farm are there followed by 35% of medium size farm and 20% of large size farm. It is seen that maximum the middle-aged farmer is evolved in the poultry farming in different size of farm. In middle age group of respondents, we founded that in 20% well doing poultry farming in small size farm, 15% were doing medium size farm and 11.25% are doing poultry farming in large size farm. In young age group 13.75% is doing poultry farming in small size farm and 12.25% in medium size farm and 6.25% in large size farm, and in old age farmer were doing poultry farming 11.25% in small size farm, 7.5% in medium size farm and 2.5% in large size farm. It is reported that 75% of respondent are living in nuclear family and 25% is living in joint family. It was founded that the annual income of small size farm is up to 20,000 and medium size farm is 20,000 to 50,000 and for large size farm the annual income is above 50000. During the survey it was reported that the marketing of poultry feed is done in two marketing channels. 37.5% respondent purchase nutrikraft poultry feed with channels I and 62.5% purchase nutrikraft poultry feed with channel-II. The marketing price of the Nutrikraft poultry feed channel I, supplied by the producer was Rs.1300 and the net price received by producer Rs.1226. Meanwhile, the cost incurred by the producer in marketing is Rs. 74, and Rs.114 as profit per 50 kg bag of poultry feed. Finally, the selling price of the Nutrikraft poultry feed 50 kg bag to the consumers was Rs.1420/bag. Eventually, the price spread was seen to be 194 rupees per bag, the marketing cost was Rs.74, the

marketing efficiency was 6.33%, producer share in consumer's Rupee is 79.29% and price spread is Rs.194. The marketing price of Nutrikraft poultry feed supplied by the whole seller was 1400, the cost of marketing incurred by the wholesalers is Rs. 40 and the net price received by the Whole seller for 1 Nutrikraft poultry feed bag is Rs. 1360 the profit margin of wholesaler is Rs. 60.00. finally, the selling price of Nutrikraft poultry feed from retailer to consumer is Rs. 1450.00 and the profit margin of retailer is Rs 50 and thus the final price for consumer is Rs. 1450. producer share in consumer's Rupee is 77.65% and price spread is Rs.224.

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